

Christmas Carries Hope Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract: The 2020 Christmas invites all the consecrated men and women around the world to celebrate it during the pandemic COVID-19 which is profoundly affecting human life around the globe. Jesus is close to His people in this period as many are affected to fear, anxiety and perhaps even despair. Jesus incarnation becomes very significant and challenging amidst the pain and struggles of the world. The God of love gave us life in sending his only son to be with us at all times and in all places so that we never have to feel lost in our struggles, pains and sickness but always can trust Him as He lives in us. During this pandemic COVID-19, as our hopes crush, and our dreams collapse, the Grace and Presence of Jesus is designed to liberate us through His Incarnation.

Keywords: Christmas, COVID-19, Hopeful Tidings, Prince of Peace

Introduction

Christmas is a time of joy and celebration of Christ the saviour being born to this world as Immanuel, *God with us*. Jesus came to dwell amidst us is the central event of Christmas. He came to share our life and death, joys and sorrows, pains and gains because we are his children. In today's world, amidst the

pandemic COVID-19, Christ the Lord beacons us His beloved children through his Incarnation not to lose enthusiasm and hope in life because He is with us even in this darkest moment of our lives.

The Meaning of Christmas

God came to us because he wanted to join us on the road, to listen to our story, and to help us realize that we are not walking in circles but moving toward the house of peace and joy. This is the great mystery of Christmas that continues to give us comfort and consolation amidst the challenges of COVID-19 through the birth of Jesus. The God of love gave us life in sending his only son to be with us at all times and in all places, so that we never have to feel lost in our struggles, pains and sickness but always can trust as he walks with us (Nouwen, 391).

Christmas stands for the presence of God with us “Immanuel” to meet the pressures of life as they come to us day by day. When our hopes crush and dreams collapse, the Grace and Presence of Jesus is designed to relieve and bring us hope. And the result is life everlasting, peace instead of restlessness, acceptance rather than guilt, love in place of lust or hate, the power to replace weakness, joy for mourning, beauty for ashes, hope for despair, courage in place of cowardice, and cleansing from all dirt and filth of spirit. Christmas brings hope, peace, and reconciliation in today’s broken world.

The Message of the Christmas

In John (3:16), we see the real Christmas message that God is giving us his only Son to the world. God gave himself fully for us without any condition. Therefore, Christmas becomes more meaningful when we give than when we expect to receive. The true spirit of Christmas is Christ-spirit must take its birth within our hearts. That is the real Christmas when we accept Christ as our personal saviour

and Lord and committing to serve those in need, to give hope to those in despair, and to spread Love, peace, joy, and message of hope in the world. Jesus is the light of the world and he is a sign of the immeasurable love and hope that God has had for all of us from the very beginning. It's a love that never stops shining even amidst utter gloom.

Challenges to the Christmas 2020

The 2020 Christmas invites all the consecrated men and women around the world to celebrate it amidst the pandemic COVID-19 which is profoundly affecting the human life around the globe. Jesus is close to His people during this period as many are affected by fear, anxiety and perhaps even despair. Jesus' incarnation becomes very significant and challenging amidst the pain and struggles of the world. Some have lost their precious lives, others have lost those whom they love, and some others have suffered through the debilitating effects of this illness, losing their jobs, their income, and most have encountered much disruption to the normal flow of their daily lives.

Isolation, contact restrictions and economic shutdown impose a complete change to the psychosocial environment in affected countries. These measures have the potential to threaten the mental health of children and adolescents significantly. Even though the current crisis can bring with it opportunities for personal growth and family cohesion, disadvantages may outweigh these benefits. Anxiety, lack of peer contact and reduced opportunities for stress regulation are the main concerns. Beside worries and anxieties related to COVID-19, the economic situation has worsened with high and rising levels of unemployment in all affected countries. This has put a lot of pressures on children, adolescents and their families and it

could result in distress, mental health problems and violence (Fegert, 2020).

At the family level, the pandemic has led to a re-organization of everyday life. All family members have to cope with the stress of quarantine and social distancing. School shutdowns have led to home-schooling and potential postponement of exams. Parents are experiencing increased pressures to work from home, to keep jobs and businesses running as well as to take care of schooling children at home at the same time, while caregiver resources including grandparents and the wider family have been restricted. Grief and mourning of lost family members, especially in cases where contact with the infected member is restricted or refused, could lead to adjustment problems, post-traumatic stress disorder, depression and even suicide of both, adults and young people. Despite the lockdown, farming continues across the country. But farmers have been facing a number of issues as of late, including a lack of the usual seasonal workers as a result of travel bans all over the world (Fegert, 2020).

In short, the current pandemic is very seriously victimizing poor, migrants, refugees, women, children, elderly, and all the vulnerable sections of the society in various ways. Domestic violence is increasing in a terrible manner day by day. These and many other traumatic human realities affect the world around which challenges every consecrated person to live our consecration radically. Are we willing to respond to these challenges generously? Today, Christ is born amidst these actualities of COVID-19. Are we the Disciples of Christ ready to celebrate the beauty, challenges, pains, struggles, death, loss, isolation, brokenness, poverty, confusion and darkness of 2020 Christmas?

Christmas Brings Hopeful Tidings Amidst COVID-19

Today, when we look at the world globally we see that the people have lost hope amidst COVID-19. It is calling the consecrated men and women to turn towards God and trust him completely to intercede for the world and to reach out to the needy. He is Immanuel *God with us* and He will not abandon his people in the darkest moment of our lives. He will speak to us tenderly in silence. The following example is very apt at this context to give us hope as well as our people who experience hopelessness amidst COVID-19. Hedwig Lewis (1994) in his book *At Home with God* narrates an incident taken from the life of the former Superior General of the Jesuit Order, Fr. Pedro Arrupe. He spent over a month in solitary confinement in the prison of Yamaguchi, Japan, in 1942, accused by enemies of Christianity of espionage and a thousand other false charges. He had been interrogated for thirty-six hours at a stretch. On Christmas Day he was feeling like it was Good Friday! Suddenly he heard many muffled, soft voices outside his prison window. And whilst some voices continued talking to deceive the guards, others sang a Christmas carol which he had himself taught his Christians. His people, heedless of the danger if they were caught, had come to console him, to tell him they were with him. Fr. Arupe burst into tears. It lasted only a few minutes. Then all was silent again. But the prince of peace had filled his heart with incredible joy and peace. He later recalled that was his happiest Christmas (Lewis, 124). He learnt what it meant to be powerless; it also taught him what joy, love and hope can bring to the broken humanity. During this COVID-19 pandemic, Immanuel is calling us to trust Him with our whole heart, mind and being.

Conclusion

Christmas marks a turning point both in the Church's Liturgical Calendar as well as in the universal civil calendar in that it stands at the junction of all that was, is and is to come! Against this backdrop, looking back at the year since last Christmas is like looking at oneself in a broken mirror that reflects nothing but the brokenness of human life, Christmas heralding the possibility of mending that brokenness. During this pandemic let us not allow the virus to affect our hearts because we have a God who is with us capable of killing all the virus in the world. He is the "Wonderful Counselor, Mighty God, Everlasting Father, Prince of Peace (Is 9: 9). He comes to us every moment to dispel the darkness of this world which is groping in utter hopelessness. Let us entrust the entire humanity into the hands of the Lord despite the uncertainties of life, so that all may find peace, joy and hope amidst COVID-19 to celebrate a meaningful Christmas 2020.

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